

Building Geospatial Knowledge Graphs for Cultural Heritage with the GeoLinks API

Nicolò Pratelli¹[0000-0003-0364-922X], Claudio De Martino¹[0009-0003-3548-5597],
Emanuele Lenzi^{1,2}[0000-0002-9159-8858], and Valentina
Bartalesi¹[0000-0001-9024-0822]

¹ Institute of Information Science and Technologies (ISTI), National Research
Council of Italy (CNR), Pisa, Italy

`nicolo.pratelli,claudio.demartino,emanuele.lenzi,valentina.bartalesi@isti.cnr.it`

² Department of Information Engineering (DII), University of Pisa, Pisa, Italy

Abstract. The Cultural Heritage domain is rich in contextual information, often found in unstructured texts. These sources frequently reference places but typically lack the semantic structure required for geospatial integration and analysis. We introduce the GeoLinks API, a lightweight web service that extracts and links geospatial entities from narrative texts to support the automatic construction of structured geospatial knowledge graphs. The API performs two core functions: (i) extracting geometries from GeoNames IRIs, and (ii) recognising and linking place entities to Wikidata. Outputs are expressed in GeoSPARQL, enabling spatial reasoning, semantic interoperability, and integration with Linked Data infrastructures. We demonstrate the performance of the GeoLinks API on a dataset of contextual narratives related to traditional craft production, illustrating how it transforms unstructured cultural texts into machine-readable, semantically enriched geospatial knowledge. This approach advances Cultural Heritage preservation and research by making spatial context explicit and supporting new forms of digital analysis.

Keywords: Geospatial Knowledge Graphs · Named Entity Linking · GeoSPARQL · Cultural Heritage Crafts · Linked Open Data

1 Introduction

Cultural heritage data are rich in contextual, spatial, and historical dimensions. Much of this information is embedded in unstructured textual sources, such as descriptions, notes, and historical or ethnographic narratives [9]. These texts frequently reference places (such as villages, regions, landmarks, and landscapes) that are essential for understanding the significance of heritage practices, material culture, and historical events. However, such references are often implicit and lack the semantic structure required for integration into geospatial data infrastructures or formal knowledge representations. Furthermore, they frequently omit critical geospatial information (i.e. coordinates, bounding boxes, or polygons) needed to accurately define a place’s location and spatial extent.

This paper introduces the GeoLinks API, a lightweight and domain-adaptable web service designed to retrieve geometries associated with specific IRIs and to extract place entities from unstructured texts. The API outputs a graph expressed in GeoSPARQL [1], enabling integration into any semantic ecosystems. By facilitating the construction of geospatial knowledge graphs from narrative sources, GeoLinks supports novel forms of spatial analysis, data enrichment, and digital storytelling within the Cultural Heritage domain.

In the sections that follow, we present the implementation of the GeoLinks API and validate its application using a dataset of ethnographic narratives related to traditional craft production, drawn from the European project Craft Understanding, Education, Training, and Preservation for Posterity and Prosperity (CRAEFT)[13].

2 Related Works

Several tools have been developed for named entity recognition and linking, such as BLINK [12], REL (Radboud Entity Linker) [11], Genre [3] and mGenre [4], which support general-purpose entity extraction from text. More recent systems like ReLiK [10] offer improved disambiguation and support for linking entities to Wikipedia, whereas the current development of modules such as spaCy Entity Linker plugin³ and Flair entity linker⁴ promise accuracy, efficiency, and flexibility in training. Furthermore, there is Wikifier [2] that is linked to the Wikipedia knowledge base. However, these tools are not specifically tailored for geospatial entities and typically lack integration with geographic resources like Geonames⁵ or OpenStreetMap⁶. There are some tools such as Irchel Geoparser⁷ and Mordecai 3 [5] that are Python libraries and they use spaCy for the Named Entity Recognition (NER) task and retrieve candidates from the GeoNames gazetteer. Furthermore, they do not produce output in geospatial RDF formats such as GeoSPARQL [1]. In parallel, efforts within the semantic web community have focused on modeling spatial data using GeoSPARQL and on developing spatial knowledge graphs, yet these approaches often rely on structured datasets rather than extracting knowledge directly from text. In the Cultural Heritage domain, most enrichment initiatives have concentrated on metadata, with limited attention given to the semantic linking of narrative content. Projects such as Europeana [6] and Pelagios [7] have demonstrated the value of linking heritage data to places, but they do not offer automated pipelines for processing unstructured texts. In contrast, the GeoLinks API addresses this gap by combining geospatial entity recognition, linking to both Geonames and Wikidata, and the automatic generation of GeoSPARQL-compliant knowledge graphs directly from Cultural Heritage narratives.

³ <https://github.com/egerber/spaCy-entity-linker>

⁴ <https://flairnlp.github.io/docs/tutorial-basics/entity-linking>

⁵ <https://www.geonames.org/>

⁶ <https://www.openstreetmap.org/>

⁷ <https://github.com/dguzh/geoparser>

3 GeoLink API

The GeoLinks API was developed with two main objectives: (i) enriching geospatial gazetteer IRIs with geometries, and (ii) extracting and geospatially enriching place entities from unstructured text. These functions support the transformation of heterogeneous Cultural Heritage data into geospatial Linked Open Data, using GeoSPARQL for interoperability and semantic reasoning.

Key design requirements included API accessibility for integration into digital heritage workflows, automatic recognition of geographic entities in text, and retrieval of corresponding geospatial data in line with Linked Open Data principles. Additionally, the system had to be lightweight and efficient, capable of running on standard hardware without reliance on high-performance GPUs.

The API is implemented in Python using the FastAPI framework⁸. Testing is performed through various endpoints to streamline and automate the process. The API can be downloaded and tested via the GitHub repository⁹.

3.1 Geospatial Enrichment of Gazetteer IRIs

In many cases, Cultural Heritage records already contain references to places, often using identifiers from sources like GeoNames. For instance, in the CRAEFT project, several place names in metadata were annotated with GeoNames IRIs. However, the public GeoNames API imposes strict rate limits, particularly problematic in high-volume or batch-processing contexts, and it only provides point coordinates and bounding boxes—lacking full geometrical representations.

To overcome these limitations, we developed a module within the GeoLinks API that enriches GeoNames references with detailed geometries (e.g., coordinates, bounding boxes, polygons). Following a Linked Open Data approach, we leveraged existing links from GeoNames to Wikipedia, Wikidata, and OpenStreetMap to access richer spatial representations. By traversing these connections, we retrieved detailed geometries from OpenStreetMap via Wikidata, effectively bypassing GeoNames' constraints and enhancing the available spatial data for integration.

This step enriches existing metadata with explicit geospatial representations, which are critical for spatial queries and visualization.

To validate the effectiveness of the module geometry extraction from semi-structured data we conducted an analysis on a subset of Cultural Heritage records from the CRAEFT project that had been manually annotated with GeoNames identifiers. We began by extracting all distinct GeoNames IRIs referenced in the knowledge base (KB). For each IRI, we queried the GeoNames public API to retrieve associated geospatial information, including the point geometry (latitude and longitude), bounding box, and, where available, polygonal representations of the place.

⁸ <https://fastapi.tiangolo.com>

⁹ <https://github.com/AIMH-DHgroup/geometry-retrieving-api>

The evaluation focused on the number and percentage of GeoNames IRIs for which geospatial data could be successfully retrieved via the GeoLinks API, as well as the types of geometries obtained. Preliminary results indicate that while all point coordinates can already be retrieved directly from the GeoNames API, only 93% of bounding boxes are available. In comparison, the GeoLinks API was able to retrieve geometries for 77% of the entities, demonstrating that a substantial proportion of annotated places were effectively enriched with additional spatial information.

These findings highlight the module’s capability to enhance metadata with explicit spatial representations, emphasizing the benefits of a federated data integration approach. Rather than relying exclusively on a single service, the GeoLinks API leverages the interoperability of Linked Data sources—specifically, the connections between GeoNames, Wikidata, and OpenStreetMap—to provide more robust, scalable, and sustainable access to geospatial data.

3.2 Place Entity Recognition and Geospatial Linking

The second and more complex task involves extracting place references from narrative texts. To this end, we developed a modular pipeline consisting of two main components: (i) a Named Entity Recognition (NER) module that identifies candidate place names, and (ii) an Entity Linking (EL) module that connects these candidates to Wikidata¹⁰ via SPARQL queries.

The NER component supports interchangeable backends, allowing adaptability across different languages and corpus types. Seven configurations are currently implemented, involving various combinations of spaCy 3.8.5, Flair, Geoparser, and REL (see Table 1). These can be used individually or combined (e.g., spaCy + Flair, REL + Flair, Geoparser + spaCy), enabling comparative evaluations and tailored deployments.

In the EL stage, SPARQL queries are generated based on the NER output and filtered to return only geospatial entities (e.g., instances of `wd:Q486972`, representing human settlements). The module first retrieves the top three candidate entities by textual label matching. These are then ranked by calculating a similarity score between each candidate’s description and the surrounding context in which the entity appears—typically the sentence or event, as defined in the gold standard. If no suitable match is identified, a fallback mechanism queries the Wiki API and selects the top-ranked result. The module outputs RDF triples in GeoSPARQL, supporting integration with semantic geospatial infrastructures.

To assess the performance of the place-extraction module from unstructured text, we conducted an evaluation using contextual narratives curated within the CRAEFT Knowledge Base (KB). These narratives, which describe traditional craft practices across Europe, consist of 462 distinct events. To construct a statistically significant gold standard, we selected a representative subset of events using the standard sample size determination formula with finite population correction [8], resulting in a final sample of 237 manually annotated events.

¹⁰ <https://www.wikidata.org>

Performance was evaluated using standard information retrieval metrics: precision, recall, and F1-score. These were applied to compare the effectiveness of each configuration in terms of both entity coverage and annotation accuracy. All seven NER configurations of the pipeline were run on the selected gold standard sample. Each configuration was further compared against a state-of-the-art baseline, with an emphasis on maintaining a lightweight and computationally efficient design suitable for standard computing environments. For this purpose, we employed the ReLiK small model [10] as the benchmark.

Table 1. Performance of extraction configurations. Bold = improvement over ReLiK-small; underline = highest per column.

Configuration	Precision	Recall	F1 Score
spaCy 3.8.5 transformer model	<u>0.78</u>	0.80	<u>0.79</u>
Flair	0.73	0.81	0.77
Geoparser	0.75	0.56	0.64
REL	0.67	0.37	0.48
REL+Flair	0.71	0.69	0.70
spaCy 3.8.5 + Flair	0.70	<u>0.87</u>	0.78
Geoparser + spaCy 3.8.5	0.70	0.73	0.71
<i>ReLiK small model (baseline)</i>	0.59	0.75	0.66

Preliminary results, presented in Table 1, show that the spaCy 3.8.5 transformer model achieves the highest F1 score (0.79), indicating the best overall balance between precision and recall. Notably, combining spaCy with Flair leads to the highest recall (0.87), which suggests it is especially effective at capturing relevant entities, though with a slight trade-off in precision. All configurations outperform the ReLiK small model baseline in F1 score (except for REL and Geoparser) highlighting the significant benefits of transformer-based and hybrid approaches in geospatial named entity recognition. These findings support the use of more recent, transformer-based NER models for improved geospatial data retrieval. In scenarios where downstream human validation is involved, a higher recall is often preferable (even at the cost of lower precision) because it ensures fewer false negatives (i.e., missed entities). Extra false positives can be quickly discarded by a human reviewer. Conversely, configurations with higher precision but lower recall may reduce noise but risk omitting relevant entities, increasing the user’s effort to manually recover them. This trade-off should guide model selection based on the intended pipeline context.

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